

B r i F a c e

H2020:MSCA-IF-2018

Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method
(H2020-MSCA-IF-2018 Marie Skłodowska-Curie)

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Coordinator: Dr S Mitoulis | **Academic Advisor:** Dr Y Wang

Industrial partners & Stakeholders: Sika A.G., Denco Structural Eng. P.C.

Duration: 24 months (start date: June 2019) | Overall budget: € 212 933,76

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223811/factsheet/en>

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D2: Career Development Plan (CDP)

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Objectives of the career development plan

1. Strengthen the research and academic profile and skills of the Fellow through the activities of Briface project and the interactions in a multicultural and diverse environment..
2. Exploit the impact of MSCA action to further expand networks with industry, stakeholders and academia.

Scientific Objectives

1. Attain high-level skills in enhancement of adhesive layer mechanical properties.
2. Learn how to correspond kinematics response with mechanical characteristics of the solid media.
3. Learn on pathologies of reinforced concrete bridges in Europe.
4. Learn on practical problems and restriction in the applications of strengthening measures.
5. Learn on modern monitoring techniques.
6. Attain skills in structural health monitoring with guided waves.
7. Attain skills in decomposing signal's noise of vibration excitations numerically.

Transferable skills-objectives

1. Attain high-level skills on how to write joint grant applications.
2. Become proficient in giving scientific lectures in various audiences.
3. Learn on how to create strategic plans for further development of scientific groups.
4. Learn how to organise dissemination events.
5. Learn how to identify new and emerging research areas.
6. Learn on how to foster mentoring of students.
7. Develop fundraising skills form stakeholders, industry or governmental bodies.
8. Develop managerial skills.

A. LONG-TERM CAREER OBJECTIVES (over 5 years):

Objectives:

1. Continuing the academic career by getting tenured in a senior role in a Higher Education (DUTh or other European University).
2. Increasing the impact of research.
3. Winning more research projects.
4. Leading research group on strengthening and monitoring systems for structures.
5. Participating in committees and international organizations for policy making/ codes' authorship, in the field of structural engineering.
6. Reviewer in more prestigious scientific journals
7. Reviewer in committees for the evaluation of research projects.
8. Participating in committees for the evaluation of Higher Education Institutions.
9. Become a member in the Institute of Civil Engineering (ICE-UK).

What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals:

1. Publication of papers
2. Participation to conferences
3. Common authorships of papers and research proposals with other scientists
4. Lectures in other Universities or stakeholders, governmental bodies or industry
5. Dissemination through web platforms (LinkedIn, ResearchGate and others).
6. Collaboration with industrial partners to develop ideas or apply the research results.
7. Creating relationship of trust with industrial partners for continuous funding of research.

B. SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES (1-2 years):

Research results

Publications:

1. Achillopoulou DV, Moltalano A and Choffat F (2021). Investigation of the bond behaviour of interfaces of FRP strengthening schemes enhanced with toughened epoxy adhesive layers applied to healthy or concrete containing corroded rebars, *Construction and Building Materials* (under review).
2. Dimitra V Achillopoulou. 'Investigation of the bond behaviour of interfaces of CFRP sheet strengthening schemes enhanced with toughened epoxy adhesive layers in corroded concrete substrates' 8th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering COMPDYN 2021, 27-30 June, Streamed from Athens, Greece.
3. Achillopoulou DV, Mitoulis SA, Argyroudis SA and Wang Y (2020). Monitoring of transport infrastructure: a road map toward resilience enhancement strategies. *Science of the total environment*, Volume 746, 1 December 2020, 141001, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141001>
4. Achillopoulou DV, Mitoulis SA (2020). Resilient Monitoring of the Structural Performance of Reinforced Concrete Bridges using Guided Waves. IABMAS 2020: 10th International conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management, Sapporo, Japan.
5. Argyroudis SA, Achillopoulou DV, Livina V and Mitoulis SA, Data-driven resilience assessment for transport infrastructure exposed to multiple hazards by integrating multiscale terrestrial and airborne monitoring systems. IABMAS 2020: 10th International conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management, Sapporo, Japan.
6. Achillopoulou DV (2019). BriFace: Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring. Presentation in the Young's Engineers Session- International Association for Bridge and Structural Engineering Congress: 'The Evolving Metropolis' New York, September 4-6. (Shortlisted for the award)

Completed conferences, workshops and presentations:

1. Member of the SC of 'Challenges for existing and Oncoming Structures' event, Prague 2022
2. Member of the SC of 'Bridges and Structures: Connection, Integration and Harmonisation', IABSE Congress Nanjing 2022.
3. 8th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering COMPDYN 2021, 27-30 June, Streamed from Athens, Greece. Chair: Session: Repair and retrofit of structures
4. Webinar: 'Can Monitoring Enhance the Resilience of Civil Infrastructure?', 13/4/2021, UK (invited lecturer and co-organizer).
5. Organizer of Special Session: SS35: Monitoring strategies for enhancing transport infrastructure resilience, IABMAS 2020: 10th International conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management, Sapporo, Japan.
6. Young Engineers Board (elected), International Association for Bridge and Structural Engineering (IABSE-UK).
7. Special Session IABMAS 2020: 10th International conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management, Sapporo, Japan.
8. Lloyd's Register Foundation International Conference 2019, London, UK.
9. International Association for Bridge and Structural Engineering Congress: 'The Evolving Metropolis' New York, September 4-6.

Anticipated/future conference, workshop attendance, courses, and/or seminar presentations:

1. Dimitra V Achillopoulou, Antonino Moltalano & Fabien Choffat (2021) 'Interface response of CFRP fabrics for concrete substrates enhanced with toughened epoxy adhesive layers.' 10th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE on FRP COMPOSITES in CIVIL ENGINEERING CICE 2020, Istanbul.
2. Dimitra V Achillopoulou. 'Effect of toughened adhesive layers in strengthening schemes for concrete elements' IABSE Symposium Prague 2022, Challenges for existing and Oncoming Structures' event, (abstract submitted).

3. University of Surrey Research seminars/presentations, October 2021

Training and other activities:

Research Skills and techniques:

- Training in resilience and risk assessment topics
- Training in monitoring techniques
- Training in installation of equipment for monitoring
- Training in installation and application of advanced FRP-based strengthening systems
- Training in Digital Image Correlation (DIC) tools.

Training on IP management

- Meetings with the Technology Transfer Office (TTO) of the University of Surrey.

Other professional training (course work, teaching activity):

- Teaching activity during the academic year 2019-2020: winter semester: module ENG2103-tutorials part.
- CPD sessions in the University of Surrey-- Introduction to teaching and learning (3 sessions)/ Assessment and Feedback (1 session)/ Fostering Students' Engagement (1 session)/ Creating Educational Videos (1 session).
- RDP seminar within the University of Surrey- Supervision Day (2 sessions).
- Graduate Certificate in Learning & Teaching program (completed, expected 10/2021).
- Health and safety training (2 sessions)-University of Surrey.
- Participation in the authorship of joint research proposals.
- Participation in research consortiums.

Anticipated networking opportunities

- ICE UK
- Centre for Smart Infrastructure and Construction, University of Cambridge
- 4TU.Resilience Engineering
- Autostrade per l'Italia
- Autobahn
- Network rail
- Transport Scotland
- Highways England
- Transport for London
- GEFYRA S.A. (Concessionnaire of the Rion - Antirion Bridge)

Other activities with professional relevance

- Meetings with Industrial partners and discussion over future products, existing practical problems and feasible solutions with high impact
- Interaction with colleagues and mentoring figures to further develop critical thinking on new research areas, the impact and use of research results in practice.
- Meetings with the members of the Centre for Educational and Academic Development (CEAD) and of the Surrey Centre for Excellence in Professional Training and Education (SCEPTrE).

Other activities

- Volunteering for sharing experience of MSCA and academia
- Participating in the Athena Swan activities within the University of Surrey
- Talks at schools and local communities.